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SONNET – SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector

D 7.2: Updated Co-creation, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy

Project Coordinator: Fraunhofer ISI

Work Package: WP7 Co-creation and dissemination: Accelerating sustainable energy transitions

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2	Dutch Research Institute for Transitions	DRIFT	NL	drift for transition
3	University of Sussex, with its Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU)	UoS	UK	US UNIVERSITY OF SUSSEX
4	Grenoble Ecole de Management	GEM	FR	G GRENOBLE ECOLE DE MANAGEMENT
5	Akademia Leona Kozminkiego	ALK	PL	KOZMINSKI UNIVERSITY
6	Zurich University of Applied Sciences	ZHAW	CH	zhaw
7	ICLEI European Secretariat	ICLEI	DE	ICLEI Local Governments for Sustainability
8	City of Mannheim	MANN	GER	STADT MANNHEIM ²
9	City of Antwerp	ANTW	BE	A City of Antwerp
10	City of Bristol	BRIS	UK	BRISTOL CITY COUNCIL
11	City of Grenoble	GREN	FR	VILLE DE GRENOBLE
12	City of Warsaw	WARS	PL	CITY OF WARSAW
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Executive Summary

The co-creation, dissemination and exploitation strategy of SONNET describes how the knowledge and experience of consortium partners will be used for communicating about the project, disseminating its results to a wide range of audiences, and ensuring that the resulting ideas, methods and recommendations are taken up and continued to be used after the project ends (exploitation). Communication and dissemination activities (WP7) will be carried out from the very beginning (M1, June 2019) to the end of the project (M36, May 2022). As such, an initial draft of this strategy was already under development in June 2019; *what follows is a mid-term update of the overall co-creation, dissemination and exploitation strategy (D7.2)*. This update considers changing landscapes, what has been achieved in this work package so far, and plans to enable SONNET to reach its co-creation, dissemination and exploitation targets moving forward. The development of the strategy is led by ICLEI Europe, with the help of all partners. It will be updated systematically to ensure its continued alignment with the evolving SONNET project.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	3
1.1	Review of communication goal: breaking down siloes	3
1.1.1	Interdisciplinarity	3
1.1.2	Transdisciplinarity	4
1.1.3	Co-creation of knowledge	5
2	Co-creation, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy	7
2.1	Objectives	7
2.2	Target Groups	7
2.3	Key messages	10
2.4	Communication strategy	10
2.4.1	Visual identity	10
2.4.2	Communication channels	12
2.4.3	Communication products	14
2.4.4	Bridging across the silos: face-to-face connections	16
2.4.5	Scientific outreach and training	17
2.4.6	Related projects and initiatives	18
3	Evaluation and Monitoring	20
4	Key Performance Indicators	21
5	Timeline	23
6	Internal Communication and Responsibilities	24
6.1	Communication amongst project partners	24
6.2	Distribution of responsibilities	24
7	Use of results after the project ends	26
	Appendix 1: EC summary requirements	27
	Appendix 2: Exploitation Roadmap	29
	Appendix 3: Pre-existing partner channels	32

Figures

Figure 1: SONNET partners and potential outreach through their respective networks	5
Figure 2: SONNET's primary target groups	8
Figure 3: SONNET's wider target groups	9

1 INTRODUCTION

SONNET's co-creation, dissemination and exploitation strategy addresses three closely related issues:

1. How to **integrate** the knowledge and experience of all partners to improve quality and ensure the relevance of SONNET's results;
2. How to **share** SONNET's work and results with different stakeholders across Europe to attract their interest and maximise uptake;
3. How to ensure the **exploitation** of the results after the end of the project.

The strategy describes the general principles and specific formats to facilitate cross-sectoral and transdisciplinary learning, based on ICLEI's long-standing experience as a knowledge-broker between different actors in the field of sustainable energy, as well as based on input of all partners (Chapter 1). It also describes project target audiences, their needs in relation to the project, key messages to be shared with them and the most suitable channels to reach them (Chapter 2). Finally, the strategy includes a continuously updated plan for the exploitation and uptake of results (Chapter 3).

1.1 Review of communication goal: breaking down siloes

Strengthening the role of social innovation in energy (SIE) transitions is a task that requires bringing different actors and types of knowledge together, reaching out to unusual suspects and breaking existing silos. This requires – and should result in bolstering – collaboration amongst different disciplines related to energy systems, such as sociology, governance, economics, policy, and innovation studies (interdisciplinarity), and different societal actors, such as academics, practitioners and municipal representatives (transdisciplinarity). This will together generate new perspectives, orientations and possible solutions to ongoing societal challenges.

Project activities target bridging the following silos in particular: (a) social innovation and energy experts; (b) SIE initiatives and local governments; (c) established and emerging energy system actors; and (d) social and technological innovation experts. SONNET considers both the academic expertise of researchers and the professional expertise of practitioners. This bridge-building nature of SONNET is reflected both in its methodology and in its dissemination activities. They are designed from inter- and transdisciplinary perspectives, with focus given: (1) to the needs of policy makers and practitioners, and (2) to bringing ideas from the local to the European level.

1.1.1 Interdisciplinarity

SONNET aims to investigate how, to what extent, and under which enabling conditions diverse types of SIE may successfully contribute to overcoming transition barriers, such as limited citizen engagement or slow adoption of new technologies. In order to achieve its overarching objective,

SONNET is developing and applying a novel interdisciplinary framework, which combines concepts and insights from 3 related fields of research: sustainability transitions research, energy research in social sciences, and social innovation research. SONNET's unique contribution to this field of research is a systematic integration of insights and concepts from all 3 of these areas.

Partners will need to use the appropriate tone and vocabulary when communicating about the project's results, to make sure the contents reach and can be used by all intended target groups. For this reason, during each project meeting, some time has been – and will continue to be – dedicated to dissemination capacity-building for the consortium. Capacity-building activities will be changed based on needs expressed by partners, and insights garnered from ongoing monitoring and reporting (with a midterm report being submitted this month), in order to target the areas in which co-creation, communication and dissemination goals are proving harder to reach.

Four consortium meetings have taken place so far, hosted (or virtually hosted) in Karlsruhe (Germany), Rotterdam (the Netherlands), Warsaw (Poland), and Zurich (Switzerland). Each meeting featured dedicated sessions to jointly discuss how best to communicate about the project and disseminate its results. These sessions have included:

- collective brainstorming of appropriate project taglines and a visual identity;
- collaborative review of dissemination tools, including which are working well, and identifying which tools need to be further developed or better utilised;
- collaboratively feeding into the design of the webinar series;
- and an interactive 2.5-hour workshop on improving and fine-tuning collaboration and communication amongst academic and local government project partners.

The discussion held as part of this most recent workshop (hosted online in January 2021) has fed into the strategy, as noted in the sections that follow.

1.1.2 Transdisciplinarity

Given the close intertwinement of social, cultural, political, economic and technical themes in SONNET's work, a transdisciplinary consortium, including universities, research institutes, an international network and city administrations, carries out this work (see Figure 1, below). The diverse backgrounds of SONNET project partners will ensure the quality of its results, as well as their relevance to target cities, and to the wider audience of local governments interested in taking up its outcomes.

Figure 1: SONNET partners and potential outreach through their respective networks

However, the meaningful inclusion of knowledge, feedback and contributions from a multitude of stakeholders spanning societal groups and actors also means that specific internal and external communication challenges must be addressed. Sophisticated internal communication will be necessary to bridge possible gaps between partners from different backgrounds and working cultures. This plan therefore addresses the challenges of both internal and external communication.

1.1.3 Co-creation of knowledge

SONNET is a research project. This means that its main results relate to new insights on the topic under investigation. However, it also covers practical implementation, by putting emerging insights into practice. The so-called ‘City Labs approach’ is thereby central to SONNET.

Project partners are investigating a variety of social innovation fields relevant for the energy transitions across 6 European countries, with a total of 18 case studies being conducted, each highlighting different SIE initiatives (showcasing a total of 36 SIE initiatives). Project partners are organising a number of face-to-face and online events to further validate and enrich project results. SONNET co-creates SIE knowledge and activities and, in the process, encourages knowledge-sharing amongst cities and associated partners. However, European countries and cities are diverse, and thus generic solutions are limited. The co-creation process thereby helps

translate insights locally, leading to more locally-relevant results, and developing a sense of ownership amongst representatives of key target groups.

In this spirit of co-creation, some of SONNET's communications take a more personal and informal tone. This includes, for example, blog posts on its [website](#), and social media posts on its [Twitter feed](#). This ensures that the project is approachable and invites co-creation of knowledge not only between partners, but also with input from other stakeholders.

In addition to generating research about and insights regarding SIE initiatives, the SONNET project also aims to provide an innovative example of the institutional dynamics needed to put SIE initiatives at the core of the Energy Union. To contribute to this goal, SONNET communication and events reach out both to local SIE initiatives, and to European-level representatives, engaging all in these processes.

2 CO-CREATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

Task 7.1, lead: ICLEI Europe, co-lead: UoS, supported by Fraunhofer ISI and DRIFT

2.1 Objectives

WP7 primarily contributes to SONNET Objective 6: “Accelerate sustainable energy transitions through: transdisciplinary co-creation of social innovation in the energy sector (SIE) in urban areas; a toolkit with practical recommendations for encouraging successful SIE; and capacity building activities for SIE actors, policy makers, academics, students and citizens”. The specific objectives of WP7 are to:

- **Coordinate** the co-creation and dissemination process and develop a co-creation, dissemination and exploitation strategy, designed to share SONNET’s results with a wide range of audiences (T7.1).
- **Build bridges** between sectors, disciplines and contexts by creating well-facilitated spaces for exchange and learning (T7.2), thereby:
 - Translating SONNET’s results into actionable recommendations for policy makers and tools empowering SIE actors (T7.3),
 - Developing and disseminating novel and cutting-edge scientific knowledge about SIE (T7.4),
 - Contributing, upon invitation by the European Commission’s Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA), to common information and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and synergies between H2020 supported actions.
- **Maximise** exploitation impact.

2.2 Target Groups

The project will prioritise the following target groups, recognising their key roles in accelerating energy transitions: policy makers, practitioners, researchers and experts (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: SONNET's primary target groups

The SONNET consortium is made-up of partners who belong to each of these target groups. This provides a unique opportunity to co-create dissemination strategies, and to collectively brainstorm the best ways to reach each group. This is a continual process, which requires regular communication internally, as well as dedicated time set aside to this end.

As one example, at a consortium meeting in Karlsruhe (October 2019), a facilitated workshop divided the consortium up into groups to more deeply explore the profiles and needs of key target audiences to identify outlets to reach each audience, the best messaging styles to use, networks to tap into, etc. The results of this initial work are as follows, and are being re-evaluated and updated regularly:

- *Policy makers*: This is a broad audience, which spans all political levels (local to European), as well as those with direct and indirect power (e.g. elected officials vs. interest groups). Policy makers will be best reached via networks, such as European communication channels, and local government networks like ICLEI. Already foreseen European-level SONNET events will be key to reaching each of these policy makers. If these are not sufficient, we will also consider hosting 'policy lunch' events that bring together policy makers to discuss in an interactive format (e.g. as part of ICLEI's flagship *Breakfast at Sustainability's* series), etc. In light of the COVID-19 pandemic, we have revisited this point, and now foresee making use of *Breakfast at Sustainability's*, as a result of limitations to in-person knowledge-sharing opportunities.
- *Practitioners*: Sub-groups within this overarching group require unique outreach (e.g. SIE employees, volunteers, members, who may be working, retired, migrants, etc.). We will approach each group by considering what SIE can bring to them in particular. Most outreach to practitioners will be via the City Labs, which are closest to citizens, associations, and local SMEs. We will make use of local social media channels in each of our SONNET cities, work places, local press, and schools to reach different groups. To this end, we have disseminated postcards, translated to all of our local languages, which make use of imagery and short, simple text, as an entry point for many practitioners to our work.

- *Researchers:* Academic members of the SONNET consortium belong to a number of existing academic communities and networks, which can be tapped to share information. These communities often convene at conferences, read similar academic publications, and use specific social networks, like ResearchGate (where SONNET now has a ‘team’ profile). Visuals, metrics and concrete numbers will help pique researchers’ attention, and should be prominently used in digital communication. This will guide the development of SONNET infographics.

Project activities and results will also target other stakeholders essential to supporting the transition process, including public and private energy utilities, citizen and community groups, financial institutions, associations and networks in the energy field, and other related actors (see Figure 3 below).

Figure 3: SONNET's wider target groups

With the support of project partners, special attention is given to the stakeholders in the six SONNET cities, including citizens and community groups, politicians and civil servants, businesses and entrepreneurs, as well as local media outlets.

2.3 Key messages

To reach as wide an audience as possible, the project uses key messages, adapted to each of its target groups. These were explored during the first project meeting from September 30 to October 2, 2019 as part of the brainstorming exercise described above (see chapter 1.1.1). They are being regularly evaluated and amended (if needed) over the course of the project, based on the consortium's experiences. Some of the messages identified include:

- *Policy makers:* SONNET provides insights on how SIEs can help reach high-level climate goals, build bridges amongst governing levels, and garner support from grassroots SIE groups.
- *Practitioners:* SIE can help lower energy bills, increase social connectedness of local communities, and support citizens to find meaning and purpose through their contributions to energy transitions.
- *Researchers:* SONNET is unique in that our research team includes both local governments and academic researchers; we thus enrich the community of inter- and transdisciplinary research, and provide a unique research perspective.

The overarching SONNET tagline, decided upon at the consortium meeting in Karlsruhe in October 2019, is simply “*Social innovation in energy transitions.*” This was deemed clean, encompassing of all of the varied facets of the project, and a good window into our work for all target audiences.

2.4 Communication strategy

The communication strategy includes an overarching project visual identity, the use of a variety of communication channels, specific communication products, scientific dissemination activities, cooperation with sister projects, and the strategic organisation of and participation in relevant events.

2.4.1 Visual identity

Part of Task 7.1, lead: ICLEI, co-lead: UoS, supported by Fraunhofer ISI and DRIFT.

The first step to an effective communication strategy is to create a coherent and pleasant visual identity for the project, so that it is unique and recognisable not only by its content but also by its appearance. This visual identity, including, among other aspects, a project logo, document templates and presentation materials, have been developed and disseminated to all partners to ensure clear external communication. Presentations at the Rotterdam and Warsaw consortium meetings served to field questions from the consortium regarding the use of the visual identity, to ensure clarity and ease of use.

A call for designers was published early in the project, in order to get professional support in creating a visual identity for SONNET, which uses fitting colours, appropriate images and impactful graphical elements, which are evocative of our main themes.

At the consortium meeting in Karlsruhe, all partners joined a collaborative brainstorming session to map out our initial ideas for this visual identity. This was shared with our designer to guide her work.

The SONNET visual identity begins with its logo, which evokes two main SONNET tenets: transition, and co-creation. The logo features our primary SONNET colour “transitioning” into our secondary colour, to evoke imagery of social and energy transitions. The rectangles in our logo remind viewers of building blocks or bricks, in reference to the co-creation aspects of the project. Similarly, the way in which our acronym is lined up evokes our full project name.

We have created 6 versions of the logo (shown below). Our primary logo is in full colour and features only the acronym SONNET (the first of the 6 versions depicted below), while other variations may be used as needed and appropriate:

Our designer also created a standard PPT template based on our logo, primary and secondary colours. This went through several rounds of revision, based on feedback and collaborative brainstorming from the entire consortium. ICLEI Europe also created a standard SONNET document template for use in deliverables and other written documents.

Visual Identity Guidelines were developed by ICLEI Europe, shared with all consortium members, and stored in our shared SONNET filing system for ease of access.

ICLEI Europe chose to work with the same designer to shape our website (described below), as well as the five SONNET infographics, which will be published intermittently throughout the project, in conjunction with the publication of Energy Reads (one published so far). This ensures that SONNET has a consistent and recognisable visual identity. All of the designer's work has been guided by inputs from the entire consortium; for example, a member of the team from DRIFT is a talented illustrator, whose sketches formed the basis of much of the imagery ultimately conveyed in the first infographic. This co-creation element will be continued in communications moving forward.

ICLEI Europe has utilised the visual identity to create other visual dissemination products, such as twitter cards.

2.4.2 Communication channels

2.4.2.1 Project website

Part of Task 7.1, lead: ICLEI, co-lead: UoS, supported by Fraunhofer ISI and DRIFT.

The SONNET website serves as a public space where project work is accessible to a large public (M6, MS13). It has been designed following the previously created visual identity, and developed with SONNET's target audiences in mind.

Text on the website will – and does – use an informal tone that invites readers in. An approachable tone, visual and easily understandable formats are paired with the publication of more technical and formal results, thereby inviting readers in, and guiding them to be able to access academic research outputs.

The website is being developed in English. It is envisaged to translate the City Lab pages into their respective languages, so that final results and materials will be accessible to a more local public. Similarly, the City Lab pages have been designed to be 'living' pages, which are updated with inputs from local partners. This will be a particular focus of the second half of the project, when City Labs will be in 'full swing' and producing results (this timeline was delayed due to extensions granted as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic).

The website (www.sonnet-energy.eu) notably includes:

- A home page with quick links to all relevant content, SONNET videos, the latest news and events;
- An 'About' page presenting the project, its goals and involved partners;
- A 'News and Events' section;
- City Lab pages, including a landing page which presents the City Lab work overall, as well as one page per city lab;

- A 'Research' page, which overviews our main research objectives and approaches;
- A 'Resources' page with subpages, which direct readers to the SONNET typology, project outputs, webinar series, and sister projects; and
- A 'Contact' page.

The website is updated regularly, with all project outputs made publicly available, and with the 'News and Events' feed kept up to date. In addition, the website back-end advises on page readability to assist with optimising each page. We will investigate complementing this with search engine optimisation in the second half of the project, to assess whether this would be a worthwhile venture given its potential impact versus costs.

The website will be kept up to date throughout the remainder of the project, and will be accessible following the conclusion of the project as well.

2.4.2.2 Social media

Part of Task 7.1, lead: ICLEI, co-lead: UoS, supported by Fraunhofer ISI and DRIFT.

In order to reach out to as wide an audience as possible, SONNET uses virtual communication channels, such as social media (M6, MS13). A dedicated **Twitter** account enables the project to share information about its activities and results, as well as general information linked to SIE and related initiatives. It has also proven to be a helpful tool for connecting with sister projects and other SIE stakeholders, and forging cross-project relationships with other Horizon2020 projects.

SONNET's twitter handle was decided collaboratively at the consortium meeting in Karlsruhe, and is @SONNET_energy. The twitter feed is updated regularly, and makes use of the visual identity. A list of partner organisations' twitter handles has been collated, and will continue to be used to amplify reach.

A dedicated SONNET "[playlist](#)" is hosted on ICLEI Europe's **YouTube** account, making use of its existing reach to draw attention to the two original videos to be produced in the framework of SONNET, as well as to webinar recordings. The first SONNET video was viewed 200 times in just the first three months that it was available online!

Partners have been encouraged to share content on their own communication channels, such as, but not limited to: Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, institutional websites, blogs or newsletters, all in an effort to maximise the dissemination of project outcomes. In particular, SONNET partners have been encouraged to disseminate insights in their local languages, to ensure that content can reach all of our target audiences.

In response to insights garnered from a co-creation workshop for the SONNET consortium in January 2021, we are currently planning workshops to support cities in crafting articles and posts to better reach local audiences (e.g. from cities' own social media channels, in local languages, addressing local press).

2.4.3 Communication products

To further increase the outreach of its dissemination of results, SONNET will use different communication products, aimed at all of its target groups, such as a project postcard and a series of practical recommendations. They are, and will continue to be, available for download on the project website, publicised through the project's and partners' communication channels, and printed versions will be distributed at events.

2.4.3.1 Project postcard

Part of Task 7.1, lead: ICLEI, co-lead: UoS, supported by Fraunhofer ISI and DRIFT.

A project leaflet was originally foreseen to be developed for SONNET. However, upon consultation with consortium members, it was clearly established that a shorter, one-page promotional 'postcard' would be more useful for all partners. This product would be smaller, thereby making it easier to carry when traveling to events, and would have less text to improve approachability. Finally, partners felt that a smaller product like a postcard would be easier to share online, in digital formats.

The postcard was developed on the basis of the visual identity elaborated in cooperation with a professional designer. It is now available in electronic and print formats, in all SONNET languages (Polish, German, Dutch, French, English).

2.4.3.2 Practical recommendations and SIE Toolkit

Task 7.3, lead: ICLEI, co-lead: UoS, supported by DRIFT and Fraunhofer ISI.

In order to facilitate the uptake of project results, SONNET will develop a mix of written and audio-visual practical recommendations to provide knowledge and tools to accelerate the energy transition, tailored to the needs of various target groups (i.e. practitioners and policymakers) (M10-M36). They will include the following types of tools:

- 5 '**Social Innovation Meets Energy Reads**' (M20-34, lead: ICLEI with the support of academic partners). These will take the form of short and accessible papers introducing main issues addressed by the project. They will distil main results and recommendations of the project from WP1-6, validated during WP7 events, and focus on the needs of different target groups. The issues to be addressed are being regularly adjusted and revisited throughout the project, but the current proposed structure is the following:
 - **#1 Social Innovation Meets Energy:** Introduction to the concept of social innovation and the roles SIE can play in accelerating energy transition, featuring examples from SONNET cities and the SONNET typology – published June 2020
 - **#2 Energising Social Innovation:** Overview of governance approaches cities can take (and are taking) to steer issues related to social innovation in energy, and to support social innovation locally, featuring examples from SONNET cities. This will

be based on Deliverable 2.1 (published in November 2020), and is expected to be completed in the first quarter of 2021.

- **#3 Social Innovation in Energy:** SIE city lab stories: summary of SONNET cities' experiences, describing lessons learned from the city labs and sharing their recommendations for other cities.
- **#4 Social Innovation in Energy Meets Europe:** How local SIE actors contribute to the achievement of European energy policy objectives and what kind of support (knowledge, funding and legislation) and enabling conditions are needed for local SIE working to enable sustainable energy transitions at the European level.
- **#5 Social Innovation Met Energy:** Summary of SONNET results, easily accessible to practitioners and policy makers, serving as a navigation tool for all relevant project outputs.
- A series of 5 **infographics**, closely linked to the 'Social Innovation Meets Energy Reads', that summarise key project results in a visual way (M10-34, lead: ICLEI with the support of academic partners).
 - The first such infographic has been published as a visual overview of the first Energy Read. It was designed and produced in partnership with the SONNET designer.
 - The next infographics are foreseen to be published alongside each Energy Read, to complement them and increase their overall reach.
- 2 short **videos** – one introducing SONNET and the diversity of SIE (M12) and the other distilling key SONNET messages (M34) in a visual and accessible way. These will be uploaded to YouTube and subtitled in local languages (lead: ICLEI with the support of cities and respective academic partners).
 - The first such video was published in October 2020, and will be subtitled in the first quarter of 2021.
 - In addition, short video clips may be produced to complement SONNET events. This is being explored as a way to make online events feel more personal, in light of physical restrictions related to the COVID-19 pandemic. So far, this idea has been considered in reference to the SONNET Power Labs, led by DRIFT.

On the basis of these practical outputs, SONNET will compile an **SIE Toolkit** (M34, lead: ICLEI with support of DRIFT), which will take the form of a navigable online publication, and will include:

1. all of the 'Social Innovation Meets Energy Reads';
2. all of the infographics;
3. a description of selected methods used within the project (e.g. the goal alignment map (T6.1), the typology of social innovations (T1.2) or methods to design and learn from experiments (T4.1 & T4.8));
4. the developed set of socio-political strategies for encouraging SIE (T2.1-T2.4).

This toolkit will be an open-access digital ‘how-to-guide’ available on SONNET’s website with partners’ websites referring to it, that describes in an accessible, non-academic language the steps needed to understand how different interests and institutions shape local energy systems and how to accelerate sustainable energy transitions, both from a single initiative perspective and a system perspective, illustrated with examples collected in WP1-6. It will include both the “what” and the “how”, sharing methods used or developed within SONNET. The publication will be organised in a modular structure, allowing each user to decide how deep they want to go or what specific theme or city they want to read about. It will be promoted via a social media campaign to increase its audience. After the project, this so-called toolkit will be digitally hosted by the DRIFT Transition Academy, and used as course material for training programmes developed as part of Task 7.4.

2.4.4 Bridging across the silos: face-to-face connections

Task 7.2, lead: ICLEI, co-lead: UoS, supported by all partners, M5-M36.

In order to communicate about the project and facilitate the uptake of its results, SONNET will organise and/or participate in a series of relevant events, fostering face-to-face connections to bridge silos and to reach a diverse mix of stakeholders across all its target groups. They will be designed to bring together relevant actors and to foster a common understanding of the diversity, processes, successes and contributions, as well as future potential of SIE. For this, SONNET will pursue five event types:

- #1: **‘Taking people-powered energy transitions from the local to the European level’** (M12, lead: ICLEI) – a Brussels-based 0.5-day event that addresses representatives of EU institutions and European networks and initiatives.
 - Due to restrictions as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, SONNET participated in an online session as part of the European Week of Regions and Cities. Although this could not be held in Brussels, it addressed a European audience, thereby seeking to serve a similar purpose. This session was set up as a ‘Participatory Lab’, which introduced participants to SIEs, used breakout rooms to explore SIE case studies in small, interactive groups, and synthesised learnings in a concluding session.
- #2: A series of 12 local events on **‘Social Innovation Meets Energy Transition’** (M9-M26, Lead: city + academic partner with support from ICLEI) organised in each of the six SONNET cities (two per city) to officially launch and close each City Lab (WP4).
 - Several City Labs have held their launch events, including Mannheim, Grenoble and Bristol. The COVID-19 pandemic presented a distinct and unforeseen challenge for City Labs, all of whom had planned to host in-person events. Moving forward, ICLEI will continue to support cities in testing new ways to shift events online, while maintaining engaging and interactive formats. This work has begun by sharing ideas for cities to consider to this end.
- #3: Two **‘SONNET on Tour’** regional workshops in the final stages of SIE city labs (M20-M26, lead: ICLEI with host cities and respective academic partners). These will be 1.5-day training workshops hosted by the SONNET cities Warsaw and Bristol. The workshops will

prominently feature and include local SIE initiatives (e.g. field trips, peer learning sessions) and target local government representatives and SIE stakeholders.

- We are closely monitoring the COVID-19 situation, and plan to host these in online or hybrid settings, if needed.
- #4: **'Social Innovation Meets Energy Transition/Europe'** (M36, lead: ICLEI). This 1.5-day final conference in Antwerp will showcase the results of SONNET to a European audience and validate SONNET's policy recommendations.
- #5: Six **'Social Innovation Meets Energy Transition'** webinars (M5-M35, lead: ICLEI), held throughout the project, focusing on pertinent topics related to SIE and the energy transition. The recorded webinars will be shared via YouTube and promoted via the project and partners' social media channels to reach additional audiences.
 - The first four webinars have been held, with recordings available on our website and YouTube page. As the COVID-19 pandemic has shifted all events online, webinar participation has changed as well. Participants seem to be, on the one hand, more accustomed to online learning, while, on the other hand, also getting fatigued by the volume of online meetings. As a result, SONNET plans to host more than six webinars in total over the course of the project, but with smaller groups of participants per webinar. This will enable the project to utilise more interactive formats (e.g. fishbowl discussions), thereby seizing the opportunity presented by having smaller groups of webinar participants keen to deeply explore more specific topics.

In addition to SONNET-organised events, the project will capitalise on the extensive networks of project partners and will present results at selected national and European events. A calendar of relevant events is shared amongst all SONNET partners, and is updated regularly. As an example, SONNET was featured during the 9th European Conference on Sustainable Cities and Towns (mannheim2020.eu), in autumn 2020.

2.4.5 Scientific outreach and training

Task 7.4, lead: UoS, co-lead: ISI, supported by: all academic partners and ICLEI, M6-M36.

To ensure that its methodologies, learnings and key results are shared across the variety of disciplines involved in SONNET and to reach out specifically to the scientific community – also beyond project lifetime – this task envisages the following dissemination activities:

- **Participation in external conferences:** All partners participate in the identification of relevant events in which the project can be presented, such as events organised by the European Commission, international conferences and workshops in the respective fields, and keep this information updated in a shared project spreadsheet. Particularly relevant conferences for SONNET are, among others, the International Sustainability Transitions conference; Behave conference; European Council for an Energy Efficient Economy; Energy and Society conference; Ecological Economics conference; Environmental and Resource Economics conference; European Association for the Study of Science and

Technology conference; International Social Innovation Research conference; and the Living Knowledge conference, among others.

- **Organisation of six special sessions at European and international conferences:** each academic partner will organise a special conference session to create visibility for the topic in different disciplinary and academic fields. We actively seek to co-organise these special sessions with researchers from related European projects (e.g. SMARTEES, PROSEU, ENERGISE, EnergyShifts, and our sister projects SocialRES, NEWCOMERS and COMETS).
- **Scientific journal publications and working papers:** Partners are encouraged and assisted in publishing project results in peer-reviewed journals and working paper series to ensure broad visibility to the scientific community. SONNET consortium members will publish through appropriate open access schemes, including as pre-publication in institutional working paper series (e.g. Fraunhofer ISI Working Papers, SPRU Working Paper Series) and upload postprints in university repositories.
- **Guest-editing a Special Issue on Social Innovation in Energy Transitions:** Based on a Call for Papers which we initiated, we invite submissions from relevant academics doing work on SIE (including colleagues from other EU projects e.g. SMARTEES, PROSEU, ENERGISE, EnergyShifts, and our sister projects SocialRES, NEWCOMERS and COMETS). Following a competitive selection process, a two-day workshop organised by UoS (currently planned for September 2021) discussing the invited contributions will allow for in-depth mutual learning and exchange of experience and lead to a collaborative output in form of a special issue in a peer reviewed scientific journal (e.g. Research Policy, Technological Forecasting and Social Change, Energy Policy).
- **Integration of SONNET results into academic teaching and practical training programmes:** University Partners will integrate SONNET findings into their teaching materials for students at all levels and seek to involve Masters' dissertations and PhD theses in the work of SONNET (so far, 1 MSc dissertation and 4 PhD candidates within SONNET). In addition, DRIFT will produce a SONNET training module to be included in their Transition Academy Courses (e.g. their Masterclass 'Energy Transition') targeted at practitioners and policy makers. Also, ICLEI will use SONNET findings in their network trainings.

2.4.6 Related projects and initiatives

To maximise outreach and increase the sharing of knowledge and experiences, SONNET is in close contact with related Horizon 2020 projects. This includes projects funded under the same call as SONNET (our sister projects SocialRES, NEWCOMERS and COMETS) and other energy - or social innovation-related projects (e.g. SMARTEES, PROSEU, ENERGISE, EnergyShifts, UrbanA).

Relationships with these projects are fostered through attending INEA cluster meetings, via social media support, working together on events (e.g. feature sister projects in SONNET webinars), and finding additional paths to support one another through regular email contact.

Project partners have long-standing experience working on social innovation and/or energy transitions and are actively involved in relevant European and global networks that gather researchers, local government representatives or social innovation frontrunners (e.g. Global

Covenant of Mayors, EU Urban Agenda, ECOLISE, Social Innovation Exchange, International Sustainability Transitions Network, Eu-SPRI and others). This ensures that SONNET results will not only be widely shared, but will also feed into ongoing and future policy processes.

3 EVALUATION AND MONITORING

The WP leader (ICLEI) will be in charge of monitoring and evaluating all activities of the project mentioned in this strategy. This includes monitoring the overall communication, but also keeping track of dissemination done by partners at local to international levels. The impact of those activities will be assessed, as well as how well they serve the project objectives and if they suitably reach their target audiences. The monitoring and evaluation process will be twofold:

- **Internal:** This refers to communication activities taken on by the WP7 core team. All communication activities will be compiled and the target reach analysed. Statistics from the website and document download history will tell us more about the most-used items and which areas of the website are potentially not (yet) optimised (number of visits, time spent on the website, where visitors are from, share of returning visitors, number of downloads, etc.). Social media statistics will shed light on the content that is most liked, shared and by whom (number of Twitter followers, tweets, impressions; views of YouTube videos, etc.). These numbers are included in all European Commission reporting. The key performance indicators (KPIs, see chapter 4) will be used to evaluate the success of communication and dissemination efforts. Evaluation forms are distributed after each project-related event to get qualitative feedback.
- **External:** This refers to communication and dissemination activities taken on by other consortium members outside of the core WP7. ICLEI Europe has created a dissemination tracking tool where each partner reports after each communication activity (publication of an article, blog, press release, attendance or organisation of an event, etc.), what was done, how many people were reached, divided by target groups (as requested by the Commission), and a link to “evidence”. All partners are responsible for filling in the tracking tool after every activity they implement, to monitor and report on all the project's activities. Compiling this information in the monitoring form will give all partners a solid perspective on target outreach. The final compiled spreadsheet is available to all partners, and regular reminders ensure that the tracker is up to date.

4 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

To make it easier to assess the effectiveness of the SONNET co-creation, dissemination and exploitation strategy, a series of KPIs was elaborated. They are described in Table 1 below, and progress towards these KPIs is noted in reporting to the European Commission. Please note that target values are stipulated for the halfway point of the project (M18), as well as for the end of the project (M36). Progress towards these targets are remarked upon, with attention given to targets which we are currently exceeding or not yet meeting:

Table 1: Overview of selected quantifiable target indicators to measure impact

Selected diss. & com. activities and their impacts	Indicator	Target Value (M18/M36)	Comments on progress so far (if appropriate)
Website	Unique views per month	500/1000	On track
Twitter	Followers	300/600	Exceeding expectations
YouTube channel	Total views	400/800	Exceeding expectations
People reached in SONNET cities	Number of people per urban area studied (x6)	500/1000 (3000/6000)	On track
People reached via European events	People attending events organised by SONNET and others	150/500	On track
Policy makers who participated in events, research activities or engagement	3 per SONNET city, 10 national level spanning 8 countries, 20 at the EU level	30/118	Greatly exceeding expectations in some SONNET cities and countries, while underperforming in others. Geography will be addressed in the second half of the project
Local co-creators and stakeholders from science, society, policy and business involved directly in engagement process in their urban area	People per SONNET city and surrounding region	40 per city (240)	On track
Stakeholders from science, society, policy and business attending webinars	Webinar attendees	100 per webinar (600)	On track
Stakeholders from science, society, policy and business attending final SIE conference	Final conference attendees	100	n/a
Share of participants of SONNET-organised events rating the content as useful for their daily work	Share based on event evaluation survey	70%	On track

Selected diss. & com. activities and their impacts	Indicator	Target Value (M18/M36)	Comments on progress so far (if appropriate)
Participants from Eastern and Central Europe	Share across SONNET events	20%	Not yet reaching our goal
Downloads of SONNET Energy Reads	Number of downloads	100/300	On track
Articles about SONNET published outside the project website	Number of articles	5/10	Exceeding expectations
Academics aware of the project activities and findings through at least 10 conference presentations plus 10 scientific papers submitted during project period (2 per academic partner) and 1 special issue guest-edited	Academics reached by each of the six academic partners through Research Gate, working papers online, conference presentations, etc.	100/250 per academic partner (600/2250 total)	On track
Project partners experienced and trained in transdisciplinary co-creation	2 people per SONNET city (x6) plus 3 per other partners (x7)	33	On track
Potential future SIE city labs generated from this project	10 from each of the two regional workshops	20	n/a

Progress toward these goals is monitored regularly, reported to the European Commission, and shapes SONNET's approach to co-creation, dissemination, and exploitation. At this midterm point, a few targets are of particular note:

- Due in large part to the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, different SONNET cities are further or less far along in the implementation of their City Labs. This, in combination with differing capacities and levels of experience, has led to discrepancies in the number of policy makers (as one example) reached at the local and national levels across SONNET cities and countries. In the second half of the SONNET project, particular attention will be paid to those areas that have not yet met communication and co-creation goals. In addition, those consortium members who are excelling will be called upon to provide insights in support of those who are still bolstering their capacity in this area.
- SONNET is not yet on track to meet its goal of 20% of all SONNET event participants coming from Central and Eastern Europe. This is, in part, because the COVID-19 pandemic has led to the postponement of many events, including several that are of particular interest to cross-border audiences (e.g. "SONNET on Tour" workshops, final SONNET conference). It does nonetheless provide an indication that outreach in Central and Eastern Europe will have to be bolstered in the coming months. This will be especially important with respect to upcoming regional ("SONNET on Tour") events, and the final conference.

5 TIMELINE

6 INTERNAL COMMUNICATION AND RESPONSIBILITIES

6.1 Communication amongst project partners

As mentioned in chapter 1, due to its transdisciplinary nature, SONNET's success will strongly rely on the quality of the communication and cooperation between its twelve full partners, and one associated partner (City of Basel).

In practice, internal communication between partners is maintained via regular online and in-person meetings, as well as regular e-mail exchanges. Internal communication channels are arranged in such a way that they are efficient, effective and tailored to project needs. This includes a range of different communications means and mechanisms, from face-to-face contacts, project meetings, to online meetings, telephone contact or teleconferences. An online knowledge management system is provided from WP8 to facilitate collaborative writing and collection, sharing, reviewing, commenting and discussing of results and other project information. On some occasions, physical meetings will coincide with international workshops, to save costs.

Internal communication is being assessed regularly, and adapted to best meet consortium needs. For example, a workshop on co-creation was held in January 2021, and led to the suggestion of a series of new ways to support internal project communication and co-creation. To follow up, ICLEI will map the focuses of each City Lab in more detail, in order to facilitate creating tandem 'buddies' of cities, who can work together on specific challenges they face in common. In addition, some of our regularly held City Council Calls will be converted into 'workshops' to tackle specific topics, such as reaching vulnerable groups, and coping with the COVID-19 pandemic.

6.2 Distribution of responsibilities

All consortium partners have a leadership position, with each academic partner and ICLEI leading a WP, and each city partner leading their city lab task (with the exception of Basel, who joins SONNET as an associated partner).

ICLEI is in charge of the editorial and publication responsibility of all communication and dissemination products, including the project website, social media accounts, postcards, and final report, among others. It has provided all partners with the project's visual identity and guidelines on how to use them, as well as promotional material and templates for documents and presentations.

Project partners are responsible for communication and dissemination on a national and local level. This includes:

- **Local webpage:** Each consortium partner must have information about the project on their website, with key information in the local language, and a link to the SONNET website.
- **Sharing:** Partners maximise the outreach of the project by sharing the communications on their own channels (web, social media, interest groups...).
- **Media:** Project partners will be responsible for national and local media engagement, using their contacts to promote the project to the national and local targets.
- **Events:** Partners will present the project and its findings at relevant events or conferences.
- **Monitoring:** All consortium partners keep a record of all activities for evaluation and monitoring purposes through the template provided by ICLEI.

To provide extra support in some of these ventures, ICLEI will organise 'tea, cookies and learning' workshops for consortium members to explore topics like social media use, and blog post writing sessions.

7 USE OF RESULTS AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

To ensure that the impacts of this work will continue after the project has been completed, SONNET will put in place the following:

- **Exploitation Roadmap:** A roadmap for the exploitation of SONNET's results is included in Appendix 2, below. The roadmap will be elaborated during the second half of the project, with a focus on different scenarios for long-term maintenance and development of project results and uptake by various beneficiaries of its impact. To assess the different possible scenarios, the intervening relevant users and stakeholders in the field will be encouraged to provide feedback. This exploitation roadmap includes the definition of a structure for spreading results and a roadmap of actions to be undertaken after the project ends. It will also include a plan to engage new communities, strengthen outputs through new projects and initiatives, and disseminate and demonstrate the benefits of the approach to policy makers and society at large.
- **Migration of SONNET toolkit:** After the end of the project, the 'SIE toolkit' will be hosted by the DRIFT Transition Academy and used as course material for training programmes developed as part of SONNET (T7.4). Thereby, this toolkit will continue to support SIE actors, policy makers, businesses and citizens to understand how different interests and institutions shape local energy systems and how to accelerate energy transitions. As the toolkit is finalised, we will investigate possibilities (and capacity) to summarise the toolkit into succinct course material, which can be used by third parties free of charge in, for example, online courses and capacity building activities.
- **Maintenance of project website:** Through the maintenance of the project website for at least three years after the project has finished, its outputs and partners will continue to be easily searchable and accessible for clarification, advice, networking or evaluation services. In addition, key outputs will be made available on partners' websites and repositories, so that they remain accessible beyond the lifetime of the project website.
- **Nomination of post-project contact points:** SONNET's PI will continue to serve as a main contact point for all SONNET related requests and will also nominate one contact point for each partner country. These will remain available beyond the lifetime of the project for knowledge transfer to interested stakeholders, such as policy makers, local administrations, think tanks, media and citizens. It will be made clear at dissemination events that further contact is possible, as well as interest in supporting new projects and initiatives.

Appendix 1: EC summary requirements

Changes with respect to the DoA

Throughout this update of SONNET's co-creation, dissemination and exploitation strategy, certain variations have been flagged. In sum, in lieu of a project brochure, a project postcard was produced instead. In addition, numerous in-person events have been moved online, and several more are expected to move online as a result of COVID-19 restrictions. Finally, extensions granted due to COVID-19 have altered some of our expected scheduling. For example, most City Labs are delayed, and therefore events and publications to amplify their results will not be most impactful at this time.

The strategy is intended to be a “living document”, so it will be regularly updated as the project progresses.

Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable is intended to be used by consortium partners to be clear about the co-creation, dissemination and exploitation strategy that was adopted at the outset of the project and what their role in it is. It is also intended for external stakeholders interested in the project or social innovation in energy transitions in general.

Short summary of results

SONNET's co-creation, dissemination and exploitation activities have been highly productive so far. A unique visual identity has been created, and applied to give SONNET a clear, unique, and recognisable presence online, on social media, in videos, and in image cards used, for example, to promote our webinar series.

4 of the 6 originally foreseen webinars have taken place with great success. This has been due, in large part, to them featuring a diversity of SONNET partners and ‘external guests’ who have provided invaluable inputs, and have helped share SONNET's research to broader audiences.

The first SONNET Energy Read and infographic have been successfully published, with the second of each expected in the first quarter of 2021. These have helped to synthesise results from SONNET's academic outputs into visually stimulating and approachable formats. In addition, and not originally foreseen, SONNET's typology has been adapted to an [interactive webpage](#), which further serves to make our work available to a wide audience.

SONNET's first video has been published, despite unforeseen filming challenges due to COVID-19. The resulting video combines animation with interviews – recorded seamlessly from partners' homes and works – while retaining SONNET's visual identity.

As City Labs and other research progresses, the SONNET team looks forward to continuing to drive internal co-creation, building bridges, and sharing knowledge widely.

Evidence of accomplishment

All deliverables and project outputs are available to download at: <https://sonnet-energy.eu/project-outputs/>. The following links provide additional or more specific evidence:

- SONNET website: <https://sonnet-energy.eu/>
- SONNET Twitter feed: https://twitter.com/SONNET_energy
- SONNET YouTube playlist: <https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PLv-mhCFisOsWm6lmbjHCu4ohbM6B2gBXu>
- SONNET ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/project/SONNET-Social-Innovation-in-Energy-Transitions>
- SONNET's first video: <https://youtu.be/Vjafxqj6IEo>
- SONNET webinar series overview and recordings: <https://sonnet-energy.eu/blog/webinar-series/>
- SONNET's first Energy Read: [About the social dimension of energy transitions](#)
- SONNET's first [infographic](#)
- SONNET postcard in [English](#), [German](#), [French](#), [Dutch](#) and [Polish](#)
- [The SONNET Typology](#)

Appendix 2: Exploitation Roadmap

SONNET partners have long-standing experience working on social innovation and/or energy transitions, and are actively involved in relevant European and global networks gathering researchers, local government representatives, and social innovation frontrunners. These include, but are not limited to, extensive involvement in the Global and European Covenants of Mayors; the EU Urban Agenda; ECOLISE; Social Innovation Exchange; International Sustainability Transitions Network; and others. Consortium members' involvement in the wider SIE community will help ensure that SONNET results are not only widely shared, but also that they are exploited for a variety of purposes, including: feeding into ongoing and future **policy processes**; contributing to the development of future **capacity building and training activities**; applied in **other relevant projects** and related fields; and more.

The Exploitation Roadmap presented below will be elaborated throughout the second half of the SONNET project. This iterative elaboration will enable SONNET to consider different scenarios for long-term development of project results, and their uptake by the various beneficiaries of the project's impacts. Consortium members will consider the project's overall findings and conclusions, as well as changing global circumstances (e.g. with respect to the COVID-19 pandemic). This will enable the partners to envisage these different scenarios that might be pursued for long-term result exploitation, and to identify the most appropriate of these scenarios.

As scenarios are identified and weighed, project partners and members of varied beneficiary groups will be encouraged to provide SONNET input and feedback. The nature of the SONNET project – which includes case studies, City Labs, and a variety of event types – lends itself well to directly engaging possible beneficiaries regarding the exploitation and wide use of project results.

The exploitation roadmap, drafted below with the intention of elaborating it iteratively in the months to come, includes the definition of a structure for exploiting results and a roadmap of actions to be undertaken after the project ends. All exploitation activities will consider engaging new communities, strengthening outputs through new projects and initiatives, and disseminating and demonstrating the benefits of the SONNET approach to policy makers and the general public.

Ensuring continued access to results

In order to facilitate the re-application, transformation and further usage of SONNET results, continued access to material is necessary.

The SONNET website will be maintained beyond the project's date of completion; furthermore, resources will be available through the project's dedicated YouTube playlist; across consortium members' own websites; and through the use of other multiplier channels, partner websites and portals.

SONNET's Principal Investigators will continue to serve as main contact points for all SONNET-related requests, and will nominate one contact point from each partner country who will remain

available beyond the lifetime of the project for knowledge transfer to interested stakeholders, such as policy makers, local administrations, think tanks, media and citizens. It will be made clear at dissemination events that further contact is possible, as well as project interest in supporting new projects and initiatives.

Through the maintenance of the project website (as described above), project outputs and partners will be easily accessible for clarification, advising, networking, or evaluation services. In addition, key outputs will be made available at the partner's websites and repositories, so that they are accessible parallel to and even beyond the lifetime of the project website.

After the lifetime of the project, the SIE toolkit – an open-access digital 'how-to-guide' – will be hosted by the DRIFT Transition Academy and used as course material for training programmes developed as part of SONNET (T7.4). Thereby, this toolkit will continue to be applied and built-upon by SIE actors, policy makers, businesses and citizens to understand how different interests and institutions shape local energy systems, and how to accelerate local energy transitions.

Exploitation activities

SONNET partners have and will continue to pursue activities to help ensure the exploitation of project results. As stated, these actions (described below) will be reviewed and added to in the months to come, in close collaboration with project beneficiaries and partners. This will include explicit exploration of how to best exploit the project's ultimate findings and conclusions, taking into account changing global circumstances.

Feeding into policy processes

SONNET results must be accessible to, and made clearly relevant for, policy-makers to ensure that they are taken up in policy processes. This will be facilitated most directly through SONNET on Tour workshops and European-level events, which will serve as key structures for sharing results with beneficiaries who can benefit from building off the project's work. The "SONNET on Tour" workshop will also constitute capacity-building elements, to train attendees in precisely how they can apply SONNET insights.

Consortium members will bring SONNET results and insights to policy makers through their prominent roles in networks like the Global and European Covenants of Mayors, the EU Urban Agenda, ECOLISE, and International Sustainability Transitions Network. Cities will not only continue to pursue their SONNET work beyond the lifetime of the project, but will share the insights garnered with other cities through these networks and other diplomatic relationships.

Contributing to capacity-building and training

SONNET's SIE toolkit will be hosted by the DRIFT Transition Academy and used as course material for training programmes. Furthermore, as an open-access, digital toolkit, this output will be available for all to use, apply, and build-upon as part of SIE trainings.

SONNET consortium members are integrating SONNET findings into their teaching materials on an ongoing basis. These lectures and materials will thus be passed on to students, researchers,

and be used in future training material after the project's completion. Some will be published under creative commons licenses, enabling the further exploitation of such lectures.

Application in other projects and research

SONNET works within a cluster of related Horizon 2020 projects. These 'sister projects' are in close contact, and are actively collaborating on webinars, events, and promotion of mutually relevant outputs. This thus lays the groundwork for SONNET results to feed into and influence other European work in the field.

A shared dissemination and exploitation spreadsheet is used by the consortium to plan and track how SONNET results are being – and will be – integrated into learning materials, presentations at conferences, publications, and more. This is not only a *dissemination* activity, in that it shares our work, but also an *exploitation* activity, which connects SONNET researchers with external stakeholders interested in re-applying and building on SONNET's findings. Through actively pursuing and tracking these opportunities, SONNET is building networks with researchers keen to build off the foundational work we are conducting.

SONNET partners will also pursue additional research opportunities – such as further Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation grants – which will enable researchers to build off of and extend SONNET's impact.

Other exploitation activities

SONNET is well set-up to ensure exploitation of results by other European projects; by researchers; and by policy makers through SONNET capacity-building workshops, European events, and active participation in relevant (city) networks. Additional potential exploitation beneficiaries will be identified in the second half of the project, as this exploitation roadmap is developed iteratively.

Appendix 3: Pre-existing partner channels

Overview of partners' pre-existing social media channels

Partner	Channel	Potential outreach (followers, subscribers, etc.)
Fraunhofer ISI	Twitter: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● https://twitter.com/FraunhoferISI ● https://twitter.com/Fraunhofer_KA YouTube: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Channel of Fraunhofer ISI ● Channel of the 3 Fraunhofer Institutes in Karlsruhe LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/fraunhoferisi	~1,300 ~50 ~250 ~5,000
DRIFT	Twitter: https://twitter.com/drifteur Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/driftfortransition/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/5261542/	~4,700 ~900 ~1,700
SPRU	Twitter: https://twitter.com/SPRU Sussex Energy Group Twitter: https://twitter.com/sussexnrggroup/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/uniofsussex Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/sussexuni/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCla0VPyqMxQx4ivzI1OfxIw Vimeo: https://vimeo.com/uniofsussex	~9,996 ~4,055 ~87,000 ~29,500 ~315 ~4,430
GEM	Twitter: https://twitter.com/grenoble_em Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/GrenobleEM/ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/grenoble_em/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCiA22pgPEWtlfTBiZunsW4g LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/grenoble-ecole-de-management/	~15,700 ~49,000 ~8,000 ~20,200 ~57,842
ALK	Twitter: https://twitter.com/KozminskiUni Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/kozminski Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/kozminskiuniversity/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/wwwkozminskiedupl Flickr: https://www.flickr.com/photos/kozminskiuni/albums LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/akademialeonakozminskiego/	~1,500 ~29,000 ~6,000 ~1,300 ~15 ~36,000
ZHAW	Twitter: https://twitter.com/zhaw Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/zhaw.ch Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/zhaw/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/ZHAWch LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/z-rcher-hochschule-f-r-angewandte-wissenschaften-zhaw- Xing: https://www.xing.com/companies/z%C3%BCrcherhochschulef%C3%BCrangewandtwissenschaften Issuu: https://issuu.com/zhaw	~6,200 ~7,700 ~4,700 ~260 ~20,500 n.n. ~40

ICLEI	Twitter: https://twitter.com/ICLEI_Europe Flickr: https://www.flickr.com/photos/iclei_europe/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/icleieurope	~15,300 ~30 ~260
MANN	Newsletter / Bürgerbrief: https://web.inxmail.com/mannheim/buergerbrief.jsp Feeds: https://www.mannheim.de/de/rss-feeds Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/StadtverwaltungMannheim Mediathek: https://www.mannheim.de/de/mediathek Twitter: https://twitter.com/mannheim_de YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/StadtMannheim Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/mannheim_de/	n.n. n.n. ~7,000 n.n. ~1,800 ~600 ~4,300
ANTW	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/visitantwerp Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/antwerpen/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/visitantwerpen Pinterest: https://nl.pinterest.com/visitantwerp/	~33,500 ~37,200 ~500 ~40
BRIS	Twitter: https://twitter.com/bristolcouncil Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/BristolCouncil Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/bristolcouncil/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/bristolcitycouncil Flickr: https://www.flickr.com/photos/bristolcouncil	~103,000 ~7,900 ~1,740 ~665 ~148
GREN	Twitter: https://twitter.com/i/web/status/1172100409147699200 Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/149306629191/posts/10157377882099192/ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/villedegrenoble/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/villedegrenoble	~40,000 ~168,000 ~18,400 ~700
WARS	Twitter: https://twitter.com/warszawa Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/warszawa/ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/fall_in_love_with_warsaw/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/warszawapl	~270,000 ~234,000 ~72,900 ~16,100